

ON TRIPLING CONSTANT OF MULTIPLICATIVE SUBGROUPS

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Abstract

We prove that any multiplicative subgroup Γ of the prime field \mathbb{F}_p with $|\Gamma| < \sqrt{p}$ satisfies $|3\Gamma| \gg \frac{|\Gamma|^2}{\log |\Gamma|}$. Also, we obtain a bound for the multiplicative energy of any nonzero shift of Γ , namely $E^\times(\Gamma + x) \ll |\Gamma|^2 \log |\Gamma|$, where $x \neq 0$ is arbitrary.

1. Introduction

Let p be a prime number, \mathbb{F}_p be the finite field, and $\mathbb{F}_p^* = \mathbb{F}_p \setminus \{0\}$. Also, let $\Gamma \subseteq \mathbb{F}_p^*$ be an arbitrary multiplicative subgroup. Such subgroups were studied by various authors (see the references in [7]). One of the interesting questions is the determination of the *additive* structure of multiplicative subgroups see, e.g., [1, 3, 4, 5, 10, 11, 12, 14]. In particular, what can we say about the size of sumsets of subgroups, that is, about the sets of the form

$$2\Gamma = \Gamma + \Gamma := \{\gamma_1 + \gamma_2 : \gamma_1, \gamma_2 \in \Gamma\}?$$

There is a well-known conjecture that the sumset 2Γ contains \mathbb{F}_p^* , provided $|\Gamma| > p^{1/2+\varepsilon}$, where $\varepsilon > 0$ is any number and $p \geq p(\varepsilon)$ is large enough. In this article we study the bigger set $3\Gamma = \Gamma + \Gamma + \Gamma$, instead of 2Γ . Let us formulate the main result of our paper.

Theorem 1. *Let p be a prime number, $\Gamma \subset \mathbb{F}_p^*$ be a multiplicative subgroup, $|\Gamma| < \sqrt{p}$. Then*

$$|3\Gamma| \gg \frac{|\Gamma|^2}{\log |\Gamma|}.$$

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It is interesting to compare Theorem 1 with a result of A.A. Glibichuk who obtained in [4] that $|4\Gamma| > p/2$ provided $|\Gamma| > \sqrt{p}$, as well as with a result from [12], which asserts that

$$\mathbb{F}_p^* \subseteq 5\Gamma, \quad \text{if } -1 \in \Gamma \quad \text{and} \quad |\Gamma| \gg \sqrt{p} \cdot \log^{1/3} p.$$

Let us say a few words about the proof. In [9] O. Roche–Newton obtained that for any set A from \mathbb{R} there are $a, b \in A$ such that

$$|(A + a)(A + b)| \gg \frac{|A|^2}{\log |A|}. \tag{1}$$

More precisely, it was proved in [9] that the common multiplicative energy (see the definition in Section 2) of $A + a$ and $A + b$ is small:

$$E^\times(A + a, A + b) \ll |A|^2 \log |A|. \tag{2}$$

The proof used the Szemerédi–Trotter Theorem from the incidence geometry. Roche–Newton calculated the number of collinear triples in the Cartesian product $A \times A$ in two different ways and comparing these two estimates gives (2). In our arguments, we use Stepanov’s method [15] in the form of Mit’kin [8] (see also [6] and [7]), which allows us to get (1), (2) for A being any multiplicative subgroup of size less than \sqrt{p} . It is easy to see that such an analog of (1) implies Theorem 1. Notice also that in the case of a multiplicative subgroup A , bound (2) is equivalent to

$$E^\times(A + 1) \ll |A|^2 \log |A|$$

because $A + a = a(A + 1)$, $A + b = b(A + 1)$, $a, b \in A$. Thus the method allows us to obtain a good upper bound for the multiplicative energy of $A + 1$ (and actually of any shift $A + x$, $x \in \mathbb{F}_p^*$, see Theorem 2 of Section 4).

2. Notation

Let $f, g : \mathbb{F}_p \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ be two functions. Define

$$(f * g)(x) := \sum_{y \in \mathbb{F}_p} f(y)g(x - y) \quad \text{and} \quad (f \circ g)(x) := \sum_{y \in \mathbb{F}_p} f(y)g(y + x). \tag{3}$$

Replacing the addition by the multiplication, one can define the *multiplicative convolution* of two functions f and g . Write $E^+(A, B)$ for the *additive energy* of two sets $A, B \subseteq \mathbb{F}_p$ (see, e.g., [16]), that is,

$$E^+(A, B) = |\{a_1 + b_1 = a_2 + b_2 : a_1, a_2 \in A, b_1, b_2 \in B\}|.$$

If $A = B$ we simply write $E^+(A)$ instead of $E^+(A, A)$. Clearly,

$$E^+(A, B) = \sum_x (A * B)(x)^2 = \sum_x (A \circ B)(x)^2 = \sum_x (A \circ A)(x)(B \circ B)(x). \quad (4)$$

Denote by $|S|$ the cardinality of a set $S \subseteq \mathbb{F}_p$. Notice that by the Cauchy–Schwarz inequality one has

$$E^+(A, B) \leq \min\{|A|^2|B|, |B|^2|A|, |A|^{3/2}|B|^{3/2}\}, \quad (5)$$

and

$$E^+(A, B)^2 \leq E^+(A)E^+(B). \quad (6)$$

In the same way define the *multiplicative energy* of two sets $A, B \subseteq \mathbb{F}_p$

$$E^\times(A, B) = |\{a_1 b_1 = a_2 b_2 : a_1, a_2 \in A, b_1, b_2 \in B\}|.$$

Certainly, multiplicative energy $E^\times(A, B)$ can be expressed in terms of multiplicative convolutions, similar to (4).

Let $\Gamma \subseteq \mathbb{F}_p^*$ be a multiplicative subgroup. A set $Q \subseteq \mathbb{F}_p^*$ is called Γ -invariant if $Q\Gamma = Q$. All logarithms are base 2. Signs \ll and \gg are the usual Vinogradov’s symbols, so $a \ll b$ means $a = O(b)$ and $a \gg b$ is equivalent to $b = O(a)$.

3. On Sumsets of Multiplicative Subgroups

In this section we have to deal with the quantity (here T stands for *collinear triples*)

$$\mathsf{T}(A, B, C, D) := \sum_{c \in C, d \in D} E^\times(A - c, B - d). \quad (7)$$

Because $E^\times(A - c, B - b) \geq |A||B|$, it follows that $\mathsf{T}(A, B, C, D) \geq |A||B||C||D|$. It turns out that there is the same upper bound for T up to logarithmic factors in the case of A, B, C, D equal some cosets of a multiplicative subgroup. The proof is based on the following lemma of Mit’kin [8], see also [13].

Lemma 1. *Let $p > 2$ be a prime number, Γ, Π be subgroups of \mathbb{F}_p^* , M_Γ, M_Π be sets of distinct coset representatives of Γ and Π , respectively. For an arbitrary set $\Theta \subset M_\Gamma \times M_\Pi$ such that $(|\Gamma||\Pi|)^2|\Theta| < p^3$ and $|\Theta| \leq 33^{-3}|\Gamma||\Pi|$, we have*

$$\sum_{(u,v) \in \Theta} \left| \{(x, y) \in \Gamma \times \Pi : ux + vy = 1\} \right| \ll (|\Gamma||\Pi||\Theta|^2)^{1/3}. \quad (8)$$

Using the lemma above, we prove the main technical result of this section. The proof is in spirit of [9].

Proposition 1. *Let p be a prime number, Γ, Π be subgroups of \mathbb{F}_p^* . Suppose that $|\Gamma||\Pi| < p$. Then*

$$\sum_{\gamma \in \Gamma, \pi \in \Pi} E^\times(\Gamma - \gamma, \Pi - \pi) \ll |\Gamma|^2 |\Pi|^2 \log(\min\{|\Gamma|, |\Pi|\}) + |\Gamma||\Pi|(|\Gamma|^2 + |\Pi|^2). \quad (9)$$

Proof. Consider the equation

$$(a - b)(a' - c') = (a - c)(a' - b'), \quad a, b, c \in \Gamma, \quad a', b', c' \in \Pi. \quad (10)$$

Clearly, the number of solutions to the equation is

$$T(\Gamma, \Pi, \Gamma, \Pi) = \sum_{\gamma \in \Gamma, \pi \in \Pi} E^\times(\Gamma - \gamma, \Pi - \pi).$$

One can assume that products in (10) are nonzero and $b \neq c$ because otherwise we have at most $O(|\Gamma|^3|\Pi| + |\Gamma||\Pi|^3 + |\Pi|^2|\Gamma|^2)$ number of solutions. Denote by σ the remaining number of solutions.

Take a parameter $\tau \geq 2$ and define

$$\Theta_\tau := \{(u, v) \in M_\Gamma \times M_\Pi : |\{(x, y) \in \Gamma \times \Pi : ux + vy = 1\}| \geq \tau\}.$$

In other words, Θ_τ counts the number of lines $l_{u,v} = \{(x, y) : ux + vy = 1\}$, $(u, v) \in M_\Gamma \times M_\Pi$ having the intersection with $\Gamma \times \Pi$ greater than τ . Obviously, if $(u, v) \equiv (u', v') \pmod{\Gamma \times \Pi}$, then the intersections of lines $l_{u,v}$ and $l_{u',v'}$ with $\Gamma \times \Pi$ coincide. By Lemma 1, we have $|\Theta_\tau| \ll |\Gamma||\Pi|\tau^{-3}$, provided $(|\Gamma||\Pi|)^2|\Theta_\tau| < p^3$ and $|\Theta_\tau| \leq 33^{-3}|\Gamma||\Pi|$. Thus

$$q_\tau := \{(u, v) : |\{(x, y) \in \Gamma \times \Pi : ux + vy = 1\}| \geq \tau\} \ll |\Gamma|^2 |\Pi|^2 \tau^{-3}, \quad (11)$$

provided $(|\Gamma||\Pi|)^2|\Theta_\tau| < p^3$ and $|\Theta_\tau| \leq 33^{-3}|\Gamma||\Pi|$. The number of all lines intersecting $\Gamma \times \Pi$ by at least two points does not exceed $|\Gamma|^2|\Pi|^2$. Thus, splitting Θ_τ into smaller sets if its required, we get upper bound (11) for q_τ with possibly bigger absolute constant, provided the only condition $(|\Gamma||\Pi|)^2|\Theta_\tau| < p^3$ holds. The assumption $|\Gamma||\Pi| < p$ implies the last inequality.

It is easy to see that for any tuple (a, a', b, b', c, c') satisfying (10), the points (a, a') , (b, b') , (c, c') lie on the same line and these points are pairwise distinct. Clearly, the number of such triples belonging the lines that have the form $ux + vy = 0$ and intersect $\Gamma \times \Pi$ does not exceed $(|\Gamma||\Pi|)^2$, so it is negligible. Thus, using (11), we see that the remaining part of the quantity σ is less than

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{u,v} |l_{u,v} \cap (\Gamma \times \Pi)|^3 &\ll \sum_{j \geq 1} \sum_{u,v: 2^{j-1} < |l_{u,v} \cap (\Gamma \times \Pi)| \leq 2^j} |l_{u,v} \cap (\Gamma \times \Pi)|^3 \ll \\ &\ll \sum_{j \geq 1} 2^{3j} \cdot |\Gamma|^2 |\Pi|^2 2^{-3j} \ll |\Gamma|^2 |\Pi|^2 \log(\min\{|\Gamma|, |\Pi|\}). \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. □

Remark 1. A careful analysis of the proof gives that one can assume that a, b, c belong to different cosets of Γ and a', b', c' are from different cosets of Π (it will be three Cartesian products of cosets instead of one in this case). In particular, the following holds

$$\sum_{\gamma \in \xi\Gamma, \pi \in \eta\Pi} E^\times(\Gamma - \gamma, \Pi - \pi) \ll |\Gamma|^2 |\Pi|^2 \log(\min\{|\Gamma|, |\Pi|\}) + |\Gamma| |\Pi| (|\Gamma|^2 + |\Pi|^2), \quad (12)$$

where $\xi, \eta \in \mathbb{F}_p^*$ are arbitrary. Of course, one can permute Γ to $\xi\Gamma$ and Π to $\eta\Pi$ in formula (12).

Proposition 1 allows us to prove new results on sumsets of subgroups, which improve some bounds from [3], see Lemma 7.3 and also Lemma 7.4.

Corollary 1. *Let p be a prime number, $\Gamma \subset \mathbb{F}_p^*$ be a multiplicative subgroup, $|\Gamma| < \sqrt{p}$. Then*

$$\left| \left\{ \frac{a \pm b}{a \pm c} : a, b, c \in \Gamma \right\} \right| \gg \frac{|\Gamma|^2}{\log |\Gamma|},$$

and for any $X \subseteq \Gamma$ one has

$$|2\Gamma + X| \gg \frac{|X|^2}{\log |\Gamma|}.$$

In particular,

$$|3\Gamma| \gg \frac{|\Gamma|^2}{\log |\Gamma|}.$$

Proof. The first estimate follows from the Cauchy–Schwarz inequality and the interpretation of the quantity $T(\Gamma, \Pi, \Gamma, \Pi)$ for $\Gamma = \Pi$ as the number of solutions to (12) with $\xi = \pm 1, \eta = \pm 1$. To get the second estimate one applies (12) with parameters $\Gamma = \Gamma, \Pi = \Gamma, \xi = \eta = -1$. We find $\gamma_1, \gamma_2 \in \Gamma$ such that

$$E^\times(\Gamma + \gamma_1, \Gamma + \gamma_2) \ll |\Gamma|^2 \log |\Gamma|$$

because by formula (7) and Proposition 1 one has

$$|\Gamma|^2 \min_{\gamma_1, \gamma_2 \in \Gamma} E^\times(\Gamma + \gamma_1, \Gamma + \gamma_2) \leq \sum_{\gamma_1, \gamma_2 \in \Gamma} E^\times(\Gamma + \gamma_1, \Gamma + \gamma_2) = T(\Gamma, \Gamma, -\Gamma, -\Gamma) \ll |\Gamma|^4 \log |\Gamma|.$$

By the Cauchy–Schwarz inequality (5), we get

$$|(\Gamma + \gamma_1)(X + \gamma_2)| \cdot E^\times(\Gamma + \gamma_1, \Gamma + \gamma_2) \geq |(\Gamma + \gamma_1)(X + \gamma_2)| \cdot E^\times(\Gamma + \gamma_1, X + \gamma_2) \geq |\Gamma|^2 |X|^2.$$

Notice that $(\Gamma + \gamma_1)(X + \gamma_2) \subseteq 2\Gamma + \gamma_1 X + \gamma_1 \gamma_2$. Moreover, $|2\Gamma + \gamma_1 X + \gamma_1 \gamma_2| = |2\Gamma + X|$. Hence

$$|2\Gamma + X| \geq |(\Gamma + \gamma_1)(X + \gamma_2)| \gg \frac{|X|^2}{\log |\Gamma|}$$

as required. □

We are going to apply the method of this section to the problems concerning decompositions of multiplicative subgroups in the future paper.

4. Generalizations

First of all, we derive a consequence of Proposition 1 concerning multiplicative energies of shifts of subgroups.

Theorem 2. *Let p be a prime number, and let Γ, Π be multiplicative subgroups of \mathbb{F}_p^* . Suppose that $|\Gamma||\Pi| < p$. Then for any $x, y \neq 0$ one has*

$$E^\times(\Gamma + x, \Pi + y) \ll |\Gamma||\Pi| \log(\min\{|\Gamma|, |\Pi|\}) + |\Gamma|^2 + |\Pi|^2.$$

Proof. Since $x, y \neq 0$, it follows that $x \in \xi\Gamma, y \in \eta\Pi$ and $\xi, \eta \neq 0$. Further it is easy to see that

$$E^\times(\Gamma + x, \Pi + y) = E^\times(\xi^{-1}\Gamma + \gamma, \eta^{-1}\Pi + \pi)$$

for any $\gamma \in \Gamma$ and $\pi \in \Pi$. Thus all energies in the left-hand side of formula (12) coincide. This completes the proof. \square

Corollary 2. *Let p be a prime number, and let Γ be a multiplicative subgroup of \mathbb{F}_p^* , $|\Gamma| < \sqrt{p}$, and Q be Γ -invariant set. Then*

$$E^\times(\Gamma + x, Q + y) \ll |Q|^2 \log |\Gamma|,$$

where $x, y \in \mathbb{F}_p^*$ are arbitrary.

Proof. Split the set Q into cosets over Γ , that is, write $Q = \bigsqcup_{j=1}^s \xi_j\Gamma$, $s = |Q|/|\Gamma|$. Then using the Cauchy-Schwartz inequality, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} E^\times(\Gamma + x, Q + y) &= \sum_{i,j=1}^s \sum_z ((\Gamma + x) \circ (\Gamma + x))(z) ((\xi_i\Gamma + y) \circ (\xi_j\Gamma + y))(z) = \\ &= \sum_{i,j=1}^s \sum_z ((\Gamma + x) \circ (\xi_i\Gamma + y))(z) ((\Gamma + x) \circ (\xi_j\Gamma + y))(z) \leq \\ &\leq \sum_{i,j=1}^s (E^+(\Gamma + x, \xi_i\Gamma + y))^{\frac{1}{2}} (E^+(\Gamma + x, \xi_j\Gamma + y))^{\frac{1}{2}} = \left(\sum_{i=1}^s E^+(\Gamma + x, \xi_i\Gamma + y) \right)^2 \\ &\leq s \sum_{i=1}^s E^+(\Gamma + x, \xi_i\Gamma + y). \end{aligned}$$

Now applying the last bound, as well as Theorem 2 (see Remark 1), we have

$$E^\times(\Gamma + x, Q + y) \ll s^2 |\Gamma|^2 \log |\Gamma| = |Q|^2 \log |\Gamma|$$

as required. □

It is interesting to compare the last theorem with results of [2] and [17] which give a pointwise bound for the multiplicative convolution of characteristic functions of multiplicative subgroups in contrary to our average estimate.

Using formula

$$E^+(\Gamma) = E^\times(\Gamma, \Gamma + 1)$$

for an arbitrary subgroup Γ ($\gamma_1(\gamma_2 + 1) = \gamma'_1(\gamma'_2 + 1) \Leftrightarrow \gamma_1\gamma_2 + \gamma_1 = \gamma'_1\gamma'_2 + \gamma'_1 \Leftrightarrow \tilde{\gamma}_1 + \tilde{\gamma}_2 = \tilde{\gamma}'_1 + \tilde{\gamma}'_2$ for any $\gamma_j, \gamma'_j, \tilde{\gamma}_j, \tilde{\gamma}'_j$ from Γ), we derive by the Cauchy–Schwarz inequality and Theorem 2 that $E^+(\Gamma) \ll |\Gamma|^{5/2} \log^{1/2} |\Gamma|$. Indeed, by (5), (6)

$$E^+(\Gamma)^2 = (E^\times(\Gamma, \Gamma + 1))^2 \leq E^\times(\Gamma)E^\times(\Gamma + 1) \ll E^\times(\Gamma)|\Gamma|^2 \log |\Gamma| \leq |\Gamma|^5 \log |\Gamma|.$$

This coincides with Konyagin’s bound [6] up to logarithmic factors.

Let us prove a generalization of Proposition 1 and Theorem 2.

In the proof we need the notion of incidences between points and lines. Let \mathbb{F}_q , $q = p^n$, be a finite field. Suppose that we have a subset \mathcal{P} of $\mathbb{F}_q \times \mathbb{F}_q$ which we call the set of points and also we have some set of lines \mathcal{L} . The number of incidences between points \mathcal{P} and lines \mathcal{L} is

$$\mathcal{I}(\mathcal{P}, \mathcal{L}) = |\{(p, l) \in \mathcal{P} \times \mathcal{L} : p \in l\}|.$$

A trivial upper bound for the quantity $\mathcal{I}(\mathcal{P}, \mathcal{L})$ can be found in [16], see Section 8.2, namely,

$$\mathcal{I}(\mathcal{P}, \mathcal{L}) \ll \min\{|\mathcal{P}||\mathcal{L}|^{1/2} + |\mathcal{L}|, |\mathcal{P}|^{1/2}|\mathcal{L}| + |\mathcal{P}|\}. \tag{13}$$

Theorem 3. *Let p be a prime number, Γ, Π be multiplicative subgroups of \mathbb{F}_p^* . Suppose that $|\Gamma||\Pi| < p$ and Q_1 is Γ -invariant, Q_2 is Π -invariant sets. Then*

$$\mathsf{T}(Q_1, Q_2, Q_1, Q_2) \ll \frac{|Q_1|^3|Q_2|^3}{|\Gamma||\Pi|} \log^2(\min\{|Q_1|, |Q_2|\}) + |Q_1||Q_2|(|Q_1|^2 + |Q_2|^2). \tag{14}$$

Proof. Let $L = \log(\min\{|Q_1|, |Q_2|\})$. We use the arguments of Proposition 1 and interpret the quantity $\mathsf{T}(Q_1, Q_2, Q_1, Q_2)$ as the number of collinear triples in $Q_1 \times Q_2$ in particular. The term $|Q_1||Q_2|(|Q_1|^2 + |Q_2|^2) + |Q_1|^2|Q_2|^2$ in (14) corresponds to degenerate triples (vertical, horizontal and lying on exceptional lines) and appears similarly as in the proof of Proposition 1. Thus, we are considering the set of lines (pairs)

$$\mathcal{L}_\tau := \{(u, v) : |\{(x, y) \in Q_1 \times Q_2 : ux + vy = 1\}| \geq \tau\}$$

intersecting $Q_1 \times Q_2$ in at least $\tau \geq 3$ distinct points and we want to obtain a good upper bound for the size of the set to estimate the number of collinear triples. Let $Q_1 \times Q_2 = \bigsqcup_{i=1}^s C_i$, where C_i are products of the corresponding cosets, $s = |Q_1||Q_2||\Gamma|^{-1}|\Pi|^{-1}$. Taking a line $l \in \mathcal{L}_\tau$ and using the diadic Dirichlet principle, we find a number $\Delta(l)$ such that

$$\tau \leq |l \cap (Q_1 \times Q_2)| \leq \sum_{i=1}^s |l \cap C_i| \leq 2 \sum_{i : |l \cap C_i| \geq \tau(2s)^{-1}} |l \cap C_i| \ll L\Delta(l)|\Omega_\Delta(l)|,$$

where

$$\Omega_\Delta(l) = \{i : \Delta < |l \cap C_i| \leq 2\Delta\},$$

and $\Delta(l) \geq 2^{-1} \max\{\tau s^{-1}, 1\}$. The number $\Delta(l)$ depends on l , but using the diadic Dirichlet principle again, we find a set $\mathcal{L}'_\tau \subseteq \mathcal{L}_\tau$, $|\mathcal{L}'_\tau| \gg |\mathcal{L}_\tau|L^{-1}$ with some fixed $\Delta \geq \max\{\tau s^{-1}, 1\}$. After that, applying the arguments of Proposition 1, we see

$$|\mathcal{L}_\tau|L^{-1} \ll |\mathcal{L}'_\tau| \ll \frac{|\Gamma|^2|\Pi|^2}{\Delta^3} \ll \frac{|\Gamma|^2|\Pi|^2s^3}{\tau^3}$$

and we have obtained (14).

Let us give another proof. Take the same family of the lines \mathcal{L}'_τ and consider a smaller family of points $\mathcal{P}' := \bigcup_{l \in \mathcal{L}'_\tau} \bigsqcup_{i \in \Omega_\Delta(l)} C_i$. Using Lemma 1, as well as the arguments of the proof of Proposition 1 again, we see that any line meets at most $|\Gamma||\Pi|\Delta^{-3}$ cells C_i . In other words, $|\Omega_\Delta(l)| \ll |\Gamma||\Pi|\Delta^{-3}$. Let us calculate the number of incidences $I(\mathcal{L}'_\tau, \mathcal{P}')$ between lines from \mathcal{L}'_τ and points \mathcal{P}' . On the one hand, any line from \mathcal{L}'_τ contains at least $\Delta|\Omega_\Delta(l)| \gg \tau L^{-1}$ number of points. Thus

$$I(\mathcal{L}'_\tau, \mathcal{P}') \gg \Delta|\mathcal{L}'_\tau||\Omega_\Delta(l)| \gg |\mathcal{L}'_\tau|\tau L^{-1}.$$

On the other hand, by estimate (13), we get

$$I(\mathcal{L}'_\tau, \mathcal{P}') \leq \sum_{i=1}^s I(\mathcal{L}'_\tau, \mathcal{P}' \cap C_i) \leq \sum_{i=1}^s \left(|\mathcal{P}' \cap C_i| |L_i|^{1/2} + |L_i| \right),$$

where by L_i we denote the lines from \mathcal{L}'_τ , intersecting C_i . Clearly, $|\mathcal{P}' \cap C_i| = |\Gamma||\Pi|$. Further since any line l meets at most $|\Omega_\Delta(l)| \ll |\Gamma||\Pi|\Delta^{-3}$ cells C_i , we see that

$$\sum_{i=1}^s |L_i| \ll |\mathcal{L}'_\tau| \cdot |\Gamma||\Pi|\Delta^{-3}.$$

Using the estimate $|\Omega_\Delta(l)|\Delta \gg \tau L^{-1}$, the Cauchy–Schwarz inequality and the lower bound for $I(\mathcal{L}'_\tau, \mathcal{P}')$, we obtain

$$|\mathcal{L}_\tau|L^{-1} \ll |\mathcal{L}'_\tau| \ll \frac{L|\Gamma|^2|\Pi|^2s}{\Delta\tau} \ll \frac{L|\Gamma|^2|\Pi|^2s}{\tau \max\{1, \tau s^{-1}\}}.$$

After some calculations we have (14). This completes the proof. □

Remark 2. Considering $T(Q_1, Q_2, \xi Q_1, \eta Q_2)$, where $\xi \neq 0, 1$ or $\eta \neq 0, 1$ one can reduce the term $|Q_1||Q_2|(|Q_1|^2 + |Q_2|^2)$ in formula (14) of Theorem 3 sometimes. For example, if Γ is a subgroup, Q is Γ -invariant set, then the corresponding error term in $T(\Gamma, Q, \xi\Gamma, Q)$, $\xi \neq 0, 1$ is $O(|\Gamma|^3|Q| + |\Gamma|^2|Q|^2)$, and thus it is negligible.

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